

CATEGORY – COMMUNITY, LIVELIHOOD

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Gjete reinflokken

Samarbeid og interaksjoner

Ulike inntektskilder

Tilleggsfôring

Kalvemerking

Kalving i innhegninger

Oppsamling

Slakt

Beiterotering

Produksjon av høy til tilleggsfôring

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 869471

CATEGORY – COMMUNITY, LIVELIHOOD

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Antall reineiere,
alder, heltid/deltid

Reineiers helse

Reinens helse

Kultur, verdier,
og tradisjoner

Tradisjonell
kunnskap;
Utdanning

Teknologi

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – CLIMATE, ENVIRONMENT

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Kalving

Brunst

Rovdyrpopulasjoner

Reintall
og reinhelse

Vårvær;
Snøsmelting;
Start vekstsesong

Sommervær;
Insekter;
Sopp

Høstvær;
Frost;
Snø og isdekning

Vintervær;
Snøforhold

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the EU
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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Landbruk

Skogbruk

Gullgraving

Gruvedrift

Torvproduksjon

Vannkraft

Vindkraft

Infrastruktur
og bosetning

Hytter og
fritidsboliger

Sommerbeite

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the EU
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CATEGORY – LAND USE

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Vinterbeite

Verne- og
friluftsområder

Jakt;
Hunder

Dyrelivsturisme,
friluftsturisme,
og agn

Leverage from
the EU
2014–2020

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CATEGORY – SOCIETY, ECONOMY, GOVERNANCE

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Reindriftens
status og rykte

Merkevarer
reindsyrprodukter

Urfolkrettigheter

Internasjonale
avtaler

Arealplanlegging

Kjøttmarked

Nasjonal
lovgivning

Kostnader
og lønnsomhet

Subsidier og
kompensasjon

Tillit
mellom aktører

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the EU
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CATEGORY – JOKERS, SURPRISES

LANGUAGE – NORWEGIAN

Effekter av
klimaendringer;
Ekstremvær

Klimatilpasning;
Grønt skifte

Pandemier og
relaterte restriksjoner

Geopolitiske
spenninger

Leverage from
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